

Monitoring Probe Deployment Patterns for Cloud-Native Applications: Definition and Empirical Assessment

Online Appendix

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This is the online appendix of the paper Alessandro Tundo, Marco Mobilio, Oliviero Riganelli and Leonardo Mariani. "Monitoring Probe Deployment Patterns for Cloud-Native Applications: Definition and Empirical Assessment." *Submitted to IEEE Transactions of Services Computing.*

Figure 1: System-oriented CPU Consumption

Figure 2: System-oriented Memory Consumption

Figure 3: System-oriented Network Input Consumption

Figure 4: System-oriented Network Output Consumption

Figure 5: Application-oriented CPU Consumption

Figure 6: Application-oriented Memory Consumption

Figure 7: Application-oriented Network Input Consumption

Figure 8: Application-oriented Network Output Consumption

Figure 9: Monitoring a VM-based Microservice Application Usage Scenario

Figure 10: Monitoring a Microservice Application Running on Kubernetes Usage Scenario

Figure 11: Monitoring Serverless Backend Functions Usage Scenario